

Characterization of 1,3-dialkyl imidazolium intercalated montmorillonites

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Manuscript received 29 December 2010, accepted 13 April 2011

Abstract : Na-Montmorillonite (Na-MMT) was intercalated with two series of dialkyl imidazolium salts. The series were selected by varying the alkyl substitutions at 1 and 3 positions of imidazole ring viz. 1-alkyl 3-methyl imidazolium salts in one series and 1-methyl 3-alkyl imidazolium salts in other series. Length of the alkyl chain was varied. Gallery heights of these imidazolium intercalated montmorillonites (I-MMT) were deduced by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD). Thermal stability and organic loading of I-MMT were studied using thermogravimetric analysis. Vibration bands due to organic inclusion within montmorillonites (MMT) were characterized by FTIR measurements. TEM analysis disclosed the microstructural changes of MMT after intercalation with organic intercalates. The properties of I-MMT were found to be influenced by alkyl chain length and their variation in 1 and 3 positions of imidazole ring.

Keywords : Montmorillonite, intercalation, gallery height, thermogravimetry, microstructure.

Introduction

During the last decade, polymer-clay nanocomposites have received intense attention from scientific and technological communities. The automotive, aerospace and packaging industries view polymer-clay nanocomposites as promising materials for the 21st century due to improved mechanical, thermal, barrier and flame-retardant properties¹⁻⁴. MMT is a 2 : 1 layered silicate mineral with high cation exchange property and very high aspect ratio. The thickness of a single MMT platelet is ~0.96 nm and lateral dimension is of few hundred nanometers. Unit cell of MMT consists of one octahedral Al³⁺/Mg²⁺ layer sandwiched between two tetrahedral Si⁴⁺ layers with variable isomorphous octahedral lattice substitution (Al³⁺ substituted by Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Cr³⁺, Fe³⁺ etc). Stacking of the unit cells occur along c-axis. The interlayer positions are occupied by exchangeable cations like Na⁺ or Ca²⁺, which balance the charge deficiency caused by isomorphous substitution. Replacement of these inorganic cations by organic cations occurs during intercalation reaction⁵. Organic intercalation changes two particular characteristics of MMT which makes it a good compatibilizer between clay mineral and hydrophobic polymer. Firstly, it changes the surface chemistry of MMT through the ion exchange with organic cations. Secondly, it increases basal

spacing which enhances intercalation. So, organic loading and basal spacing of intercalated-MMT are important properties. These intercalated MMT are important class of inorganic-organic hybrid which can be used as nanofillers in polymer composite. Besides it can be used as adsorbents for organic pollutants, rheological control agents, electric appliances, in waste water treatment, as thickening and gelling agent in paints, lubricants, ointments⁵ as drug delivery vehicle in medicinal field etc.⁶. MMT intercalated with alkyl ammonium salts are the most significant class of organic-inorganic hybrid used in polymer nanocomposite. Limited thermal stability of (~250 °C) these clay-intercalate hybrids reduces the expected improvements in properties (physical and flammability) of polymer-clay nanocomposites⁷. A few studies found that alkyl imidazolium intercalated MMT survive at much higher temperatures and were proven to be used in high melting point polymer/clay composites^{8,9}. But in depth understanding about the effects of structural variation of alkyl imidazolium salts on the properties of intercalated MMT is necessary. Positional interchange of alkyl substituent in 1,3-dialkyl imidazolium salts may exert an impact upon the properties of the intercalated-MMT. In the present study detailed characterization has been done to realize the changes in properties of intercalated-MMT

with the influence of positional interchange of alkyl substituents in 1,3-dialkyl imidazolium salts. The work on structure-property relationship of intercalates and intercalated hybrids have a great relevance in focusing the role of organically modified MMT as nanofillers in the clay-polymer nanocomposites.

Results and discussion

XRD studies :

The arrangement of organo-cations in clay interlayer is elucidated by X-ray diffraction analysis. Experimental MMT showed the d spacing of 001 plane (d_{001}) 1.25 nm. The smectite group of minerals shows variable integral series of basal spacing (d_{001}) which is dependent upon the size of exchangeable cation and on the degree of hydration of the cation¹⁰. The plots showed increment of basal spacing upon intercalation (Figs. 1 and 2). The gallery height ' Δ ' (Δ = thickness of organic layer sand-

wiched between two clay layers) was calculated by subtracting the average thickness of one MMT layer (0.96 nm) from d_{001} . The van der Waals thickness of a methyl group is ~ 0.4 nm. The Δ values are furnished in Table 1. The Δ values of Im_3C_2 and Im_3C_6 were found to be 0.32 and 0.48 nm, which leaves no option except that the alkyl chains with imidazolium ring lie flat along the

Fig. 1. XRD plots of Im_3C_2 - Im_3C_{12} series.

Fig. 2. XRD plots of Im_1CH - Im_3C_8 series.

Table 1. Results of XRD

Intercalated clay	Basal spacing d_{001} (nm)	Gallery height (nm)	Interlayer arrangement
Im_3C_2	1.28	0.32	Monolayer
Im_3C_6	1.44	0.48	Monolayer
Im_3C_{12}	1.92	0.96	Bilayer
Im_1CH	1.31	0.35	Monolayer
Im_1C_3	1.42	0.46	Monolayer
Im_1C_8	1.47	0.51	Monolayer

clay flake surfaces in monolayers with the planes of the zigzag carbon chains parallel to the plane of clay mineral. Im_3C_{12} showed Δ value 0.96 nm, which predicted a bilayer arrangement because the amount of increment is nearly double the monolayer spacing. Similarly, XRD plots of Im_1CH - Im_1C_8 showed mainly monolayer arrangement. But basal spacing corresponding to higher order arrangement i.e. parafinic arrangement was not observed in I-MMT. It was probably because of the fact that the effective volume occupied by imidazolium ring system was less which made the clay layers less separated from each other. In all the I-MMT, the trend of increment of basal spacings with the increment of alkyl chain length was maintained. All the XRD peaks were more or less sharp and single which indicated that the interlayer arrangements were homogeneous.

Thermogravimetric studies :

The thermogravimetric studies of raw montmorillonites indicated two major temperature regions of mass loss at around 200 °C and 500–800 °C which is the characteristic of such type of clay minerals^{11,12}. TGA curve of imidazolium intercalated montmorillonites are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The onset decomposition temperature was deduced from the plots which disclosed the extent of thermal stability of respective I-MMT. [Onset organic decomposition temperature of I-MMT was up to 335 °C

Fig. 4. DTG plots of Im_3CH - Im_3C_8 series.

(Table 2)]. If full intercalation was assumed under experimental conditions, then the difference between total weight loss and structural water loss is an indicative of

Table 2. Table for organic loading and thermal stability of I-MMT

I-MMT	Onset decomposition (°C)	Organic loading (mass%)
Im_3C_2	294	(19 - 4) = 15
Im_3C_6	335	(18 - 4) = 14
Im_3C_{12}	243	(30 - 4) = 26
Im_1CH	295	(16 - 4) = 12
Im_1C_3	328	(19 - 4) = 15
Im_1C_8	308	(23 - 4) = 19

organic inclusion into the structure. Organic loading has been furnished in Table 2. The organic loading values were dependent on chain length. Alkyl groups with C12 and C8 chain length showed higher organic loading value of 26 and 19 mass% respectively. I-MMT showed multiple mass loss peaks during DTG. This indicated stepwise organic decomposition of I-MMT. Different temperature regimes for different mass loss steps have been identified with maximum peak decomposition temperatures and given in Table 3. However, the loss at higher temperature range (> 500 °C) included structural water (4 mass%) as well as organic components of the I-MMT under investigation. Another important observation made from the DTG plots of I-MMT was that I-MMT with same series of imidazoliums showed same pattern and peak region of dehydroxylation whereas for different series of intercalates, it varied. The group of 3-methyl substituted dialkyl imidazolium intercalates dehydroxylated in between 540–700 °C whereas that of 1-methyl substituted one is in between 565–700 °C. Figs. 3 and 4 disclosed that peak nature and positions were also distinctly different for 3-methyl and 1-methyl substituted dialkyl imidazolium intercalated MMT. 3-Methyl substituted alkyl imidazolium intercalated MMT showed a single and relatively broad decomposition peak within dehydroxylation region whereas 1-methyl substituted one showed three multiple sharp peaks within the same temperature region. So, positional variation of alkyl chains in alkyl imidazolium ring influenced the pattern and position of decomposition peaks.

FTIR studies :

The FTIR spectra of I-MMT have been furnished in Figs. 5 and 6. Each class of imidazolium salts showed their own characteristic bands along with the structural clay band pattern and positions. All the structural clay bands were somewhat shifted compared to that of the untreated raw MMT. In Im_3C_n series, the bands at 3270 and 3470 cm^{-1} were due to structural -OH and interlayer water stretching vibrations^{13,14}. Peaks at 2869 and 2934 cm^{-1} were characteristic symmetric and asymmetric CH_2 stretching bands¹⁵. Bands at lower frequency region such as 850 cm^{-1} and 925 cm^{-1} were due to bending vibrations of structural -OH bonds. At 1092 and 1168 cm^{-1} , there were two characteristic bands due to Si-O symmetric and

Table 3. Organic loss values at different decomposition steps

Intercalated	Step I			Step II			Step III			Step IV		
	Temp.	OL	T_{max}	Temp.	OL	T_{max}	Temp.	OL	T_{max}	Temp.	OL	T_{max}
Im_3C_2	403–507	6	452	590–657	3	626	–	–	–	–	–	–
Im_3C_6	400–509	6	462	563–655	3	611	–	–	–	–	–	–
Im_3C_{12}	215–390	13	297	560–698	9	629	–	–	–	–	–	–
Im_3CH	290–460	5	368, 406	460–530	2	481	560–695	5	628	–	–	–
Im_3C_3	350–420	2	393	420–503	5	470	545–602	2	580	602–687	4	645
Im_3C_8	290–414	6	332	505–560	2	530	570–628	3	601	628–690	4	657

Fig. 6. FTIR plots of Im_3CH - Im_3C_8 series.

asymmetric stretching vibrations^{13,14}. In Im_1C_n series, all the above said bands were present but they were also slightly shifted.

Microstructural study :

HRTEM images, shown in Fig. 7, revealed morpho-

Fig. 7. HRTEM plot of raw MMT.

logy of untreated Na^+ -montmorillonite showing crystalline aggregates with no preferred orientation. Thin particles attached to the edges of the aggregate disclosed well defined layer stacking separated by a regular van der Waal gaps or galleries. Variation of structures can be revealed by both fringe contrast and fringe spacing. Equal contrast manifests arrangement of same orientation along c-axis. The interlayer spacing has been found ~ 1.3 nm from HRTEM images. The range of d spacing has been got rather than a single value emphasizes minor local variation in measured d spacing from various TEM images as layer stacking inhomogeneity are there. Imidazolium intercalated MMT (Im_1C_8) showed similar layer structured micrograph (Fig. 8). The d spacing value was found to be 1.4 nm (Im_1C_8) which showed less local variation compared with that of raw MMT. This manifested that structural heterogeneity is somewhat less in I-MMT. The value of d spacing also supported that the imidazolium intercalates took monolayer arrangement with in interlayer space of MMT. The values obtained from HRTEM has been compared with that of XRD. The slight

Fig. 8. HRTEM plot of raw Im₁C₈.

variation of the values has been attributed to the influence of interlayer hydration on the *d* spacing of the montmorillonite samples¹⁶.

Conclusion :

(i) Thermal stability of most of I-MMT was above 300 °C. The organic loading showed increasing trend with the alkyl chain length of dialkyl imidazolium group. Pattern and position of thermal decomposition peaks were altered with the positional variation of alkyl groups in 1,3 position of 1,3-dialkyl imidazolium intercalates.

(ii) Gallery height increased with the alkyl chain length of the alkyl imidazolium ring and imidazolium moiety took monolayer arrangement with in interlayer space.

(iii) TEM analysis supported the information gathered from XRD. It showed less local variation in interlayer spacings in I-MMT thereby rendering single *d* spacing value.

Experimental

Materials :

Montmorillonite ‘M’ (PGV, Nanacor, USA) was used in this study because of its high CEC which is primarily responsible for effective intercalation. It has been used in sodium (Na⁺) form. Intercalates were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, UK. These can be grouped into two sets. In first set (Im₃C_n), methyl group at 3 position of the imidazolium ring is kept fixed and chain length of alkyl group at 1-position varied. In 2nd set (Im₁C_n), alkyl chain at 1-position was kept fixed as methyl and chain length of alkyl group was varied in 3-position. In Im₃C_n set, the

alkyl group was varied as C₂H₅, C₆H₁₃ and C₁₂H₂₅, and marked as Im₃C₂, Im₃C₆, Im₃C₁₂. In Im₁H, Im₁C₃ and Im₁C₈, there was varying alkyl chain at 3-position such as H, C₃H₇, C₈H₁₇. The general structures of intercalates have been given in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Structure of imidazolium salts of both series.

Methods :

As received MMT was converted to sodium-montmorillonite by ion exchange with Amberlite-120 in Na⁺ form. Cation exchange capacity of the experimental montmorillonite (M) was found to be 88 cmol kg⁻¹ ^{17,18}.

Preparation of I-MMT :

1 g clay was dispersed in 250 ml deionised water and ultrasonicated (0.5 W cm⁻²) for 60 min at temperature ~70–80 °C. Then the suspension was stirred on a hot plate set at ~70–80 °C. 200 ml intercalate solution (M/100) was added dropwise into this suspension. After addition of intercalate, it was kept under constant stirring at ~70–80 °C for 1 h. The reaction mixture was kept overnight for settling. The supernatant water with excess surfactant was decanted and the flock was redispersed in water. The process was repeated for 3 times. Then it was filtered under suction and washed with 2000 ml hot water. The collected product was dried at 70 °C in vacuum drier for ~24 h. The dried product was ground in an agate mortar pestle and kept in sealed glass bottles.

X-Ray diffraction :

The studies on basal spacing of MMT and intercalated MMT was done in XPERT-PRO (PANALYTICAL)

diffractometer system. The system was operated at 30 mA, 40 kV between 2.0 to 10.0 (2 θ) at a step of 0.05.

Thermogravimetry :

TG-DTG analyses of the samples were obtained using instrument NETZSCH STA 409 C. The system was operated at a heating rate 10.0 °C min⁻¹ from 40 °C up to 1050 °C in presence of air with ~12 mg sample in alumina crucible. α -Al₂O₃ was used as a reference material.

FTIR :

Fourier transform infrared spectra (FTIR) have been measured with the Shimadzu, FTIR-8300, Japan, using KBr pellet.

HRTEM :

Transmission electron microscopy studies of the raw and intercalated clay has been performed using a Tecnai G² 30 S-T transmission electron microscope. The filament of the instrument is of lanthanum hexaboride (LaB₆). The instrument has a line resolution and point resolution 0.14 nm and 0.20 nm respectively and has been operated at 300 kV during the investigation.

Acknowledgement

The work was supported by CSIR fellowship grant to Saheli Ganguly (currently working as Senior Research Fellow in CGCRI, Kolkata). Authors would like to thank XRD, Instrumentation and TEM Section of CGCRI for providing the characterization facilities.

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